

The Kairawan Project

An open-access federated search index for Arabic and Islamic manuscripts

URL: <https://kairawan.org>

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About

Kairawan is a non-profit volunteer initiative aimed at researchers and practitioners in the discovery, indexing, and tahqiq of Arabic and Islamic manuscripts. The platform federates catalog records from nine major institutional sources into a single unified search, currently covering approximately 270,000 records.

Indexed collections

- Bibliothèque nationale de France (Gallica)
- Bayerische Staatsbibliothek (Munich)
- Princeton University Library (Garrett Collection and related)
- Vatican Apostolic Library (DigiVatLib)
- Hill Museum and Manuscript Library (vHMML Reading Room)
- West African Arabic Manuscript Database (UC Berkeley)
- Fihrist (UK union catalog)
- Princeton Geniza Lab
- Gunnar Jarring Collection (Lund University)

Technical foundations

Metadata harvest via OAI-PMH, IIIF Presentation manifests, and source-specific REST endpoints. Every record carries a canonical URL, schema.org structured data, and is reachable via an open REST API. Attribution and source-collection licenses are preserved per record.

License

Catalog metadata is rebroadcast under each source institution's terms. Platform descriptive content (this record) is CC-BY-4.0.